

**REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS has NO JURISDICTION over NORTHERN CYPRUS.
The ONLY Country Having JURISDICTION over NORTHERN CYPRUS is TRNC.**

Alexy FLEMMING; version: 03.08.2025-01

[1] Northern Cyprus IS a LEGAL (de jure) country:

**THE LEGITIMACY of the TURKISH REPUBLIC of NORTHERN CYPRUS (TRNC) is
RECOGNIZED WORLDWIDE:
(INTERNATIONAL COURT RULINGS and NATIONAL COURT DECISIONS of
VARIOUS COUNTRIES)**

■ **No prohibition of declarations of independence in international law:**

The International Court of Justice (ICJ) Ruling on Kosovo (2010; No prohibition of declarations of independence in international law):

**“THERE IS NOTHING IN INTERNATIONAL LAW THAT PROHIBITS
DECLARATIONS OF INDEPENDENCE, and the RECOGNITION OF A STATE IS A
POLITICAL MATTER.”**

The United States of America (USA), in the ICJ's 2010 Kosovo ruling, rejected the Greek Cypriot stance and issued a statement favorable to the Turkish Cypriots:

Harold Hongju Koh (The USA's representative in the UN-ICJ 2010 Kosovo case on behalf of the USA): “The argument advanced by Cyprus against the legality of Kosovo's unilateral declaration of independence is incorrect. Cyprus attempted to compare the 1244 process to the 'heartbreaking but misleading situation' of a parent sending their young child into state care, never to see them again. I argued, however, that a more accurate analogy would be the futile attempt by the state to **FORCIBLY RETURN AN ADULT CHILD TO AN ABUSIVE HOME WHEN THE CHILD NO LONGER WISHES TO RETURN**, especially after the parent and child have **LONG LIVED APART**, and **REPEATED ATTEMPTS AT RECONCILIATION HAVE REPEATEDLY FAILED**. In such a case, as here, a **DECLARATION OF INDEPENDENCE WOULD BE THE ONLY VALID OPTION** and would undoubtedly be lawful.”

<https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/141/141-20091208-ORA-01-00-BI.pdf>

(Page38; Paragraph40)

Accordingly, the US Federal Court (on 9 October 2014) declared the TRNC as a **“DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC** with a president, a prime minister, a **LEGISLATIVE** body, **AND A JUDICIARY.**”

In the UN-ICJ 2010 Kosovo ruling, ICJ Judge Trindade: “The emphasis has shifted from the **STATUS OF THE TERRITORIES** to the **NEEDS AND DESIRES OF THE PEOPLE.**”

<https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/141/141-20100722-ADV-01-08-EN.pdf> (Page550; Paragraph66)

■ Legality of the acts of the TRNC’s authorities:

The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR; 2 July 2013):

“Although the regime in the northern area lacks international recognition, **THE DE FACTO RECOGNITION OF THE REGIME’S ACTIONS IN THE NORTH MAY BE NECESSARY FOR PRACTICAL PURPOSES.** Therefore, the adoption of civil, administrative, or criminal legal measures by the authorities of the ‘TRNC’, and their application or enforcement within the territory of the regime in the north, may be seen as having a **LEGAL BASIS IN DOMESTIC LAW** for the purposes of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR).”

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-122907>

■ The United States FEDERAL COURT and The USA COURT OF APPEALS:

The United States Federal Court (9 October 2014):

“...Although the US does not recognize the TRNC as a state, it can be said that the TRNC purportedly operates as a **DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC** with a president, prime minister, **LEGISLATURE AND JUDICIARY**...The TRNC is **NOT** vulnerable to a lawsuit in Washington.”

Courthouse News Center 13.10.2014: Property Spat Over Turk-Controlled Cyprus Fails:

<https://www.courthousenews.com/property-spat-over-turk-controlled-cyprus-fails/>

USA's Federal Court: Michali Toumazou, Nicolas Kantzilaris and Maroulla Tompozou versus Republic of Turkey and **Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus**:

<http://dockets.justia.com/docket/district-of-columbia/dcdce/1:2009cv01967/139002>

USA's Federal Court Toumazou et al v. Republic of Turkey and **Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus**:

<https://docs.justia.com/cases/federal/district-courts/district-of-columbia/dcdce/1:2009cv01967/139002/53>

Greek Cypriot Toumazou applied to the USA Court of Appeals. **The USA Court of Appeals REJECTED** Toumazou, too on 15.01.2016:

<https://media.cadc.uscourts.gov/judgments/docs/2016/01/14-7170-1593754.pdf>

After the US Federal Court called and qualified TRNC as “Democratic Republic” and the USA Court of Appeals affirmed the decision, The United States Secretary of State has started to describe the **TRNC** as **the Area Administered by Turkish Cypriots**:

<https://www.state.gov/reports/2022-report-on-international-religious-freedom/cyprus/area-administered-by-turkish-cypriots/>

■ The legality, independence, and impartiality of the TRNC's courts:

The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR; 2 September 2015):

223: “When an act of the “TRNC” authorities was in compliance with **LAWS IN FORCE WITHIN** the territory of **northern Cyprus**, those acts should in principle be regarded as having a legal basis in domestic law for the purposes of the Convention”

(PS: Here, the ECtHR, by referring to the “laws in force within the territory of northern Cyprus”, means the laws enacted and enforced by the TRNC in northern Cyprus (see the ECtHR's 02July2013 ruling).

237: “the Court has already found that the **COURT SYSTEM** set up **in the “TRNC”** was to be considered to have been “**ESTABLISHED BY LAW**” with reference to the

“constitutional and legal basis” on which it operated, and ECtHR has **NOT** accepted the allegation that the “TRNC” courts as a whole lacked independence and/or impartiality”

(PS: According to the ECtHR, **the courts of the TRNC are INDEPENDENT AND IMPARTIAL.**)

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-155000>

■ United Kingdom High Court (3 February 2017):

“There was **NO DUTY** in UK law upon the Government **TO REFRAIN FROM RECOGNISING NORTHERN CYPRUS**. The United Nations itself works with Northern Cyprus law enforcement agencies and facilitates co-operation between the two parts of the island...The cooperation between the UK police and legal institutions in Northern Cyprus is **LAWFUL**.”

<http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2017/02/03/criminals-fleeing-british-justice-can-no-longer-use-cyprus-safe>

http://ambamarblearch-media.com/sites/default/files/dpp_files/TT.pdf, Page6.

■ The difference of TRNC than Transnistria, Abkhazia, and Crimea:

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR; 25 June 2024)

[Ukraine v. Russia Case (Crimea); Applications 20958/14 and 38334/18] explained the reasons for the legality of the actions of TRNC laws in the north of Cyprus under the ECtHR framework (Why the situation of the TRNC differs from that of Crimea, Transnistria, and Abkhazia):

930: Whereas the Court held that “TRNC Domestic Law” was based on the Anglo-Saxon legal tradition and was therefore accepted as “law” for the purposes of the Convention, in cases concerning Transdnierstria (the “MRT”), the Court found “no basis for assuming that [in the ‘MRT’] there is a system reflecting a judicial tradition compatible with the Convention similar to the one in the remainder of the Republic of

Moldova". The Court has reached similar conclusions regarding the "law" of Abkhazia and the "lawfulness" of Abkhaz courts.

932:...Moreover, while the "MRT" and Abkhaz-related cases concerned the "law" of unrecognised entities that did not reflect "a judicial tradition ... similar to the one in the remainder of the Republic of Moldova" or "to the rest of Georgia" respectively, in *Cyprus v. Turkey* (merits) the Court held that **"The civil courts operating in the 'TRNC' were in substance based on the Anglo-Saxon tradition and were not essentially different from the courts operating before the events of 1974 and from those which existed in the southern part of Cyprus"**. This particular aspect makes the latter case similar, yet **DIFFERENT FROM THE PRESENT CASE**. The *Cyprus v. Turkey* case concerned **THE CONTINUED APPLICATION OF PRE-EXISTING CYPRIOT LAW** valid in the territory of the "TRNC" before Turkey had obtained actual control of that territory, whereas the present case concerns the application in Crimea of the law of the Russian Federation (or the "law" of the local authorities, as its derivative) replacing the previously applicable and valid Ukrainian law.

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-235139>

[2] ALL LAWS OF TURKISH REPUBLIC OF NORTHERN CYPRUS ARE ACCEPTED IN EUROPE (EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS; ECtHR). MORE IMPORTANTLY: The ONLY COUNTRY THAT HAS JURISDICTION in northern Cyprus is TURKISH REPUBLIC OF NORTHERN CYPRUS:

2.1 In north of Cyprus island, the laws of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus are valid (TRNC DOES HAVE jurisdiction in north of Cyprus island):

ECtHR's (European Court of Human Rights) Decision (02.07.2013; Nicos PAVLIDES; Application no:9130/09. Spyridon GEORGAKIS; Application no:9143/09): "...notwithstanding the lack of international recognition of the regime in the northern area, a de facto recognition of its acts may be rendered necessary for practical purposes. Thus, **THE ADOPTION BY THE AUTHORITIES OF THE "TRNC" OF CIVIL, ADMINISTRATIVE OR CRIMINAL LAW MEASURES, AND THEIR**

APPLICATION OR ENFORCEMENT WITHIN THAT TERRITORY, may be regarded as **HAVING A LEGAL** basis in **DOMESTIC LAW** for the purposes of the Convention".

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-122907>

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22sort%22:%5B%22kupdate%20Descending%22%5D,%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-122907%22%5D%7D>

Note: In the related ECtHR's decisions above, the case applications of **the Greek Cypriots** was **IMMEDIATELY REJECTED**; i.e., their applications were found **INADMISSABLE**. That is to say, the Greek Cypriots were expelled by ECtHR just at the beginning; therefore, the cases of the Greek Cypriots were not handled (no sessions were held) by ECtHR at all.

2.2 ALL the people of Rep. of Cyprus (even the President of RoC) MUST apply to the LEGAL SYSTEM of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) about an issue related with north Cyprus in order to take their cases to the ECtHR:

ECtHR's decision [04.01.2011, (Archibishop) Chrysostomos II, Application no:66611/09]: "the procedure before the Immovable Property Commission ("IPC"), and further appeal to the "TRNC" High Administrative Court, provided for in Law 67/2005, were to be regarded as "domestic remedies" of the respondent State and that **NO GROUND OF EXEMPTION** has been established in that regard".

"NO GROUND OF EXEMPTION" and (in the last part) "Court unanimously Declares the **APPLICATION INADMISSIBLE**" means **"EXHAUST ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES OF TRNC (Northern Cyprus) first, before coming to ECtHR"**.

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-103100>

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/sites/eng/Pages/search.aspx#%7B%22fulltext%22:%5B%22Chrysostomos%22%5D,%22documentcollectionid2%22:%5B%22CASELAW%22%5D,%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-103100%22%5D%7D>

2.3 The Courts of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus are INDEPENDENT and IMPARTIAL:

ECtHR's decision (02.09.2015; Kyriacou TSIKKOURMAS AND OTHERS; Application no:13320/02): "...the **COURT SYSTEM** in the **"TRNC"**, including both civil and criminal

courts, reflected the judicial and common-law tradition of Cyprus in its functioning and procedures, and that the **“TRNC” COURTS** were thus to be considered as **“ESTABLISHED BY LAW”** with reference to the “constitutional and legal basis” on which they operated...the Court has already found that the **COURT SYSTEM** set up in the **“TRNC”** was to be considered to have been “established by law” with reference to the “constitutional and legal basis” on which it operated, and it has **NOT ACCEPTED THE ALLEGATION** that the **“TRNC” COURTS** as a whole **LACKED INDEPENDENCE** and/or **IMPARTIALITY**...when an act of the “TRNC” authorities was in compliance with **LAWS IN FORCE WITHIN THE TERRITORY OF NORTHERN CYPRUS**, those acts should in principle be regarded as having a legal basis in domestic law for the purposes of the Convention..”

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-155000>

[https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22sort%22:\[%22kupdate%20Descending%22\],%22it%22:\[%22001-155000%22\]}](https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#{%22sort%22:[%22kupdate%20Descending%22],%22it%22:[%22001-155000%22]})

Note: Here, what ECtHR means by “laws in force within the territory of northern Cyprus” is the laws that TRNC published and put into implementation (See: ECtHR’s 02.07.2013 decision above).

2.4 The Reasons why JUDICIAL LEGAL SYSTEM of TRNC in Northern Cyprus under the ECtHR framework is LEGAL in ECHR whereas LEGAL SYSTEMS in Transnistria, Abkhazia, and Crimea are ILLEGAL in in ECHR:

- i) TRNC DOMESTIC LAW WAS BASED ON THE ANGLO-SAXON LEGAL TRADITION**
- ii) THE CONTINUED APPLICATION OF PRE-EXISTING CYPRIOT LAW BY TURKISH CYPRIOT AUTHORITIES AFTER 1974**

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR; 25 June 2024)

[Ukraine v. Russia Case (Crimea); Applications 20958/14 and 38334/18] explained the reasons for the legality of the actions of TRNC laws in the north of Cyprus under the ECtHR framework (Why the situation of the TRNC differs from that of Crimea, Transnistria, and Abkhazia):

930. Whereas the Court held that “**TRNC DOMESTIC LAW**” **WAS BASED ON THE ANGLO-SAXON LEGAL TRADITION** and was therefore accepted as “law” for the purposes of the Convention, in cases concerning Transdniestria (the “MRT”), the Court found “no basis for assuming that [in the ‘MRT’] there is a system reflecting a judicial tradition compatible with the Convention similar to the one in the remainder of the Republic of Moldova”. The Court has reached similar conclusions regarding the “law” of Abkhazia and the “lawfulness” of Abkhaz courts.

932....Moreover, while the “MRT” and Abkhaz-related cases concerned the “law” of unrecognised entities that did not reflect “a judicial tradition ... similar to the one in the remainder of the Republic of Moldova” or “to the rest of Georgia” respectively, in *Cyprus v. Turkey* (merits) the Court held that “The civil courts operating in the ‘TRNC’ were in substance based on the Anglo-Saxon tradition and were not essentially different from the courts operating before the events of 1974 and from those which existed in the southern part of Cyprus”. This particular aspect makes the latter case similar, yet **DIFFERENT FROM THE PRESENT CASE**. The *Cyprus v. Turkey* case concerned THE CONTINUED APPLICATION OF PRE-EXISTING CYPRIOT LAW valid in the territory of the “TRNC” before Turkey had obtained actual control of that territory, whereas the present case concerns the application in Crimea of the law of the Russian Federation (or the “law” of the local authorities, as its derivative) replacing the previously applicable and valid Ukrainian law.

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-235139>

2.5 In north of Cyprus island, the ONLY country that has jurisdiction (i.e., whose laws are valid) is TURKISH REPUBLIC OF NORTHERN CYPRUS:

European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), (Page29; Article 35/1 Admissibility criteria):
 “The Court may **ONLY** deal with the matter after **ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES** have been exhausted, according to the generally recognised rules of international law.”

http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Admissibility_guide_ENG.pdf

In order to apply to ECtHR for an issue related in Poland, ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES of Poland MUST be exhausted. Similarly:

In order to apply to ECtHR for an issue related in north of Cyprus island, ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus MUST be exhausted.

If the legal domestic system of Republic of Cyprus had any validity in north of Cyprus, then before taking the case to the ECtHR, ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES of Rep.of Cyprus MUST have been exhausted AS WELL besides those of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. Since, according to ECtHR, legal system of Republic of Cyprus has NO validity (RoC has NO JURISDICTION) in the northern Cyprus island, **ECtHR accepts cases from northern Cyprus part of the Cyprus island AS SOON AS ALL DOMESTIC REMEDIES of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus are exhausted.**

[3] In “Simon Mistriél AYKUT v. RoC” case, the essence of the case is: THE (property) RIGHTS of Greek Cypriots (living in S.Cyprus) in NORTH OF THE CYPRUS ISLAND.

Different HATS of the DEFENDERS of the rights of the RELEVANT Greek Cypriots (living in s.Cyprus) in NORTH OF THE CYPRUS ISLAND in “Simon Mistriél AYKUT v. RoC” case does NOT change:

- i) the JURISDICTION AREA of THE PROPERTIES in the case: North of Cyprus island, and
- ii) the JURISDICTION AUTHORITY of THE PROPERTIES in the case: Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus!

ECtHR (04.01.2011, Archbishop Chrysostomos II, Application no:66611/09): WITHOUT ANY EXCEPTION, ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS MUST APPLY TO THE AUTHORITY OF TRNC for a property in north of Cyprus island.

In “Simon Mistriél AYKUT v. RoC” case, if Elena KLEOPA had been “the ADVOCATE of the RELEVANT Greek Cypriots who has the relevant properties in north of Cyprus island” instead of “the PROSECUTOR of RoC” then Elena KLEOPA would have been IMMEDIATELY REJECTED:

ECtHR (04.01.2011, App.No:66611/09): WITHOUT ANY EXCEPTION, ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS MUST APPLY TO THE AUTHORITY OF TRNC for a property in north of Cyprus island.

THE PRACTICAL REAL position of Elena KLEOPA is THE DEFENDER of the relevant Greek Cypriots WHETHER THE HAT SHE WEARS IS “the ADVOCATE of the RELEVANT people” or “the PROSECUTOR of RoC”!

“The JURISDICTION AREA of THE PROPERTIES” and “the JURISDICTION AUTHORITY of THE PROPERTIES” do NOT change based on the HAT DEFENDER WEARS!

“ECtHR (04.01.2011, AppNo:66611/09): **WITHOUT ANY EXCEPTION, ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS MUST APPLY TO THE AUTHORITY OF TRNC for a property in north of Cyprus island**” does **NOT** change when **THE DEFENDER** of the relevant Greek Cypriots changes his/her hat from **ADVOCATE** to **PROSECUTOR**!

“WITHOUT ANY EXCEPTION, ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS” means not only the-PRIVATE-INDIVIDUAL-Greek-Cypriots but also the-Greek-Cypriot-PUBLIC-ORGANIZATION(The RoC state)!

Action of people does NOT change their intrinsic rights when they act as PRIVATE INDIVIDUALS or PUBLIC ORGANIZATION (STATE).

“ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS” in “ECtHR (04.01.2011, AppNo:66611/09): WITHOUT ANY EXCEPTION, ALL GREEK CYPRIOTS MUST APPLY TO THE AUTHORITY OF TRNC for a property in north of Cyprus island” DOES INCLUDE the Greek Cypriot Elena KLEOPA (RoC's PROSECUTOR)!

The MANDATORINESS/COMPULSORINESS of applying TRNC's authorities (TRNC's Courts; TRNC's IPC etc.) exist for both the PRIVATE INDIVIDUAL Greek Cypriots and the COLLECTIVE ORGANIZATION of the PRIVATE INDIVIDUAL Greek Cypriots (The RoC state)!

[4] Türkiye's INTERVENTION on Cyprus in 1974 leading to the CURRENT DIVISION/PARTITION of the Cyprus island is LEGAL:

In 1974, Türkiye launched a military intervention in Cyprus following a coup d'état orchestrated by the Greek junta, aimed at uniting the island with Greece (Enosis).

i) Treaty of Guarantee of 1960

Türkiye acted on Cyprus via Article IV(2) Treaty of Guarantee ("In the event of a breach of the provisions of the present treaty, Greece, Turkey and the United Kingdom undertake to consult together with respect to the representations or measures necessary to ensure observance of those provisions. **IN SO FAR AS COMMON OR CONCERTED ACTION MAY NOT PROVE POSSIBLE, EACH** of the three **GUARANTEEING POWERS** reserves **THE RIGHT TO TAKE ACTION** with the sole aim of re-establishing the state of affairs created by the present Treaty."), hence in compatible with Art. 2(4) UN Charter.

ii) The firsthand decisions of The Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe (PACE) (29.07.1974)

PACE(29.07.1974, Resolution 573): "The Turkish military **INTERVENTION** was the exercise of a **RIGHT EMANATING FROM AN INTERNATIONAL TREATY** and the fulfilment of a **LEGAL** and **MORAL** obligation."

iii) Greece's court decisions (21.03.1979)

Athens Court of Appeals (21.03.1979; Case No: 2658/79): "The Turkish military **INTERVENTION** in Cyprus, which was carried out in accordance with the Zurich and London Accords, was **LEGAL**. Turkey, as one of the Guarantor Powers, had the right to fulfill her obligations. The real culprits ... are the Greek officers who engineered and staged a coup and prepared the conditions for this **INTERVENTION**."

Note: Just after 5 years later than 1974, in 1979, Greece's Highest Court decided Turkish military intervention is legal without making any difference between 1st and 2nd military operation.

iv) Makarios (Then-President of Cyprus) speech during the period covering both the coup and the intervention

Makarios (the UN Security Council Speech, 19 July 1974): **“CYPRUS WAS INVADED BY GREECE”**. Sound record of the speech:

<http://www.cypnet.co.uk/ncyprus/history/republic/makarios1.wav>

v) Applications of NO sanctions

Till now, there is NO sanction applied on Türkiye due to 1974 Cyprus war.

If a country invades another one, UN imposes sanctions on that country. Iraq invaded Kuwait, and UN imposed sanctions on Iraq. Türkiye did not invade Cyprus, hence UN did not impose any sanction on Türkiye.

vi) The NON-appearance of phrase “invasion” in UN Security Council resolutions

There is no UN Security Council resolution that calls the Türkiye’s 1974 action as “invasion”.

[5] The VOLUNTARY Population Exchange Agreement between Greek Cypriots and Turkish Cypriots UNDER THE AUSPIECES OF THE UNITED NATIONS (02.08.1975):

ALL Turkish Cypriots living in southern Cyprus chose to settle in northern Cyprus in 1975.

ALMOST ALL of the Greek Cypriots living in northern Cyprus chose to settle in southern Cyprus in 1975.

(Maronites in Northern Cyprus: Kormakitis, Karpaseia, Asomatos, Agia Marina villages. Greeks in Northern Cyprus: Rizokarpaso, Agios Andronikos, Agia Triada villages).

ALL activities (SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, POLITICAL, SPORTIVE, CULTURAL, JUDICIAL etc.) in southern Cyprus are governed ONLY by Greek Cypriots since 1974.

ALL activities (SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, POLITICAL, SPORTIVE, CULTURAL, JUDICIAL etc.) in northern Cyprus are governed ONLY by Turkish Cypriots since 1974 (**even since 1963!**).

On 15.11.1983, Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus declared its INDEPENDENCE from the Republic of Cyprus.

ALL Greek Cypriots (Tasos Asproftas, Marianna Petrakidou etc.) **were REJECTED to return back to nCyp and settle in Northern Cyprus by ECtHR:**

ECtHR (Tasos Asproftas, Application no. 16079/90, 04.10.2010; Marianna Petrakidou, Application no. 16081/90, 04.10.2010): The **PROPERTIES** from which Greek Cypriots had migrated in Northern Cyprus are **NO LONGER THEIR HOMES**, as they have been **LIVING ELSEWHERE FOR ALMOST THEIR ENTIRE LIFE** and they do **NOT** have **CONCRETE AND PERSISTING LINKS** to the properties they claim.

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-98684>

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-98688>

Since the **PROPERTIES** from which Greek Cypriots had migrated in Northern Cyprus are **NO LONGER THEIR HOMES**, the place where these properties are located (**Northern Cyprus**) is **NOT** the **HOMELAND** of these **Greek Cypriots**.

[6] Self-Determination of Turkish Cypriots

The right to self-determination is a cornerstone of international law, as established in the UN Charter and various human rights instruments

[UN-ICJ 2010 Kosovo ruling, ICJ Judge: "**The emphasis has shifted from the STATUS OF THE TERRITORIES to the NEEDS AND DESIRES OF THE PEOPLE.**"]

<https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/141/141-20100722-ADV-01-08-EN.pdf> (Page550; Paragraph66)].

Turkish Cypriots constitute a distinct people with the right to self-determination, which they exercised in establishing the TRNC.

Turkish Cypriots have formed their own institutions, government, and military, exercising **EFFECTIVE** control over northern Cyprus.

The Republic of Cyprus has NO jurisdiction on north of Cyprus island due to The SELF-DETERMINATION and INDEPENDENCE of Turkish Cypriots.

[7] Effective Control and Governance

International law recognizes the concept of **EFFECTIVE CONTROL** when determining the jurisdiction and legitimacy of state governance. Since 1974, the Republic of Cyprus has NOT exercised any effective control over northern Cyprus (**this NON-EXERCISING even dates back to 1963 when the UN separated the Greek Cypriots and the Turkish Cypriots via the Green Line!**).

The TRNC governs the territory, enforces laws, and provides services; hence, the Republic of Cyprus has NO jurisdiction over north of Cyprus island.

The principle of effectiveness in international law is a key aspect of sovereignty.

If a state does NOT effectively govern a territory, its claim to that territory are questioned, especially when another entity (such as the TRNC) is governing and providing administration FOR NEARLY HALF A CENTURY.

[8a] RECOGNITION and LEGALITY are two DIFFERENT things:

Lack of international recognition of the TRNC does NOT legitimize the Republic of Cyprus's jurisdiction over northern Cyprus.

ICJ 2010 Kosovo decision: "**RECOGNITION** is a **POLITICAL** act."

The UN Security Council's Resolution 541 (1983) and Resolution 550 (1984) denounced the unilateral declaration of independence by the TRNC; but, UN ICJ (**the United Nations International Court of Justice**) 2010 Kosovo decision: "**THERE IS NOTHING IN INTERNATIONAL LAW THAT PROHIBITS DECLARATIONS OF INDEPENDENCE**".

Hence, the resolutions **541** (1983) and Resolution **550** (1984) are **POLITICAL instruments, NOT the binding legal judgments**.

The resolutions 541 (1983) and Resolution 550 (1984) have NOT changed the reality that the Republic of Cyprus does NOT exercise control over northern Cyprus.

[8b] European Court of Justice: “The UNSC 1983/541 is NON-BINDING”

On 04.08.1986, Greece filed a case against the Council of the European Communities (supporter intervener: Commission of the European Communities). In the case, Greece first argued that the **UN Security Council Resolution 1983/541** called “upon all States not to recognize any Cypriot State other than the Republic of Cyprus”. Greece then reasoned that since the Turkish Government recognized the **Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus**, the European Community “cannot grant it the special aid without ignoring that breach and thereby itself violating an obligation imposed on it under a measure which is binding on it by virtue of the principle of substitution.”

Source: Adam Saltzman. (2019), “Developing the principle of non-recognition”.

https://digitalcommons.onu.edu/onu_law_review/vol43/iss1/1

On 25.05.1988, Council of the European Communities (supporter intervener: Commission of the European Communities) specified that the UN Security Council Resolution 1983/541 which is **not passed under Article VII of the UN Charter** is **non-binding** in nature, and Council of EC and the Commission of the EC stated that “It is manifest from the wording of the operative part and from the debates and the declarations of vote prior to the adoption of Resolution No 541 that **THE RESOLUTION DOES NOT CONSTITUTE A “DECISION” AND IS THEREFORE NOT A BINDING MEASURE**, but a measure in the nature of a **MERE RECOMMENDATION**. Consequently, the States to which the declaration is addressed are **NOT** bound to comply with paragraph 7 of the resolution or to infer from the fact that paragraph 7 was not complied with the consequences which Greece claims they should infer.”

Source: Advocate General Mancini (1988) “Opinion of the Advocate-General (of CoEC and CEC)”.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:61986CC0204>

On 27.09.1988, European Court of Justice (ECJ) rejected all of the Greece’s arguments in the Case 204/86 (Greek Republic v. Council of the European Communities (supporter intervener: Commission of the European Communities)), and punished Greece to pay all the costs, including the costs of the intervener. ECJ stated (in prg28) that the Resolution 1983/541 of the United Nations Security Council is completely extraneous to relations between the Community and Turkey.

Source: European Court of Justice (ECJ). (1988) "Judgment of 27.9.1988 - Case 204/86".

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:eec1dbbe-ca2b-4e87-9f06-d9a2d2b31a10.0002.03/DOC_1&format=PDF

[9] Diplomatic Efforts and Lack of Resolution to Cyprus Issue:

Numerous diplomatic efforts have been made to resolve the Cyprus issue, including the Annan Plan (2004), which proposed reunification under a federal system.

While Greek Cypriots overwhelmingly rejected 2004-Annan-Plan, Turkish Cypriots accepted it. This had showed the willingness of Turkish Cypriots on SHARED governance while the insistence of Greek Cypriots on NON-SHARING governance although 1960-Cyprus Republic was formed by BOTH Greek Cypriots and Turkish Cypriots TOGETHER.

The failure of reunification efforts (SINCE 1963) proves that the Republic of Cyprus's claim to jurisdiction over the ENTIRE island INCLUDING the northern Cyprus is UNFEASIBLE.

[10] PASSAGE OF TIME and EFFECTIVE CONTROL

The current status quo in northern Cyprus has existed for nearly five decades. Given the passage of time and the fact that Turkish Cypriots have exercised EFFECTIVE governance during this period, the Republic of Cyprus's INABILITY to reclaim jurisdiction shows that the ROC's claim has NO GROUND under the principle of EFFECTIVE control.

The UN Peacekeeping Force in Cyprus (UNFICYP) operates along the buffer zone between the Republic of Cyprus and Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, EFFECTIVELY recognizing the division and the INABILITY OF EITHER SIDE to exercise jurisdiction BEYOND their respective areas of control.

The territory of Northern Cyprus functions under the EFFECTIVE governance of the TRNC.

[11a] According to the fundamental principles of international law and the jurisprudence of the International Court of Justice of the United Nations:
SOVEREIGNTY OF A NATION AND ITS STATE/COUNTRY DOES NOT NEED THE CONFIRMATION OF THE OTHER NATIONS/COUNTRIES

- Sovereignty is an **EXISTENTIAL RIGHT** of the nation; it is **NOT granted** by any external authority.
- **International law RECOGNIZES AND SAFEGUARDS the right of people to SELF-DETERMINATION.**
- External recognition is **NOT** a constitutive element of sovereignty according to judicial decisions.

Recognition of sovereignty is **merely** a **diplomatic** act;

Sovereignty itself, however, **derives FROM THE WILL OF THE PEOPLE**.

Sovereignty attains its legitimacy NOT from external validation, but from within—that is, from the collective will of the nation itself. Sovereignty does not require confirmation, for **sovereignty constitutes AN INHERENT AND NATURAL LEGAL STATUS**.

1) Recognition and Sovereignty are Distinct:

Recognition is a **political** act, NOT a constitutive element of STATEHOOD. According to the Montevideo Convention on the Rights and Duties of States (1933), a political entity is A STATE if it has: (i) A permanent **population**, (ii) a defined **territory**, (iii) a government, and (iv) The **capacity** to enter relations with other states.

Montevideo criteria do NOT include “recognition” as a requirement for Sovereignty. Sovereignty **exists independently of** whether or not it is acknowledged by third parties.

TRNC satisfies the Montevideo criteria for statehood.

2) The UN Charter (1945) (Article 1; clause 2): “The Purposes of the United Nations is to develop friendly relations among nations based on respect for the principle of **EQUAL RIGHTS** and **SELF-DETERMINATION OF PEOPLES**, and to take other appropriate measures to strengthen universal peace”

The UN Charter (1945) (Article 55; clause 3) “With a view to the creation of conditions of stability and well-being which are necessary for peaceful and friendly relations among nations based on respect for the principle of equal rights and self-determination of peoples, **the United Nations shall promote universal respect for, and observance of, HUMAN RIGHTS and FUNDAMENTAL FREEDOMS FOR ALL WITHOUT DISTINCTION AS TO RACE, SEX, LANGUAGE, OR RELIGION.**”

3) The United Nations General Assembly (14.12.1960; Resolution 1514 (XV)): “ALL PEOPLE have the right of self-determination.”

(The self-determination right is a **PERMANENT** right).

4) International Court of Justice (ICJ) (Advisory Opinion on Kosovo; 2010)

ICJ: **“International law contains NO prohibition on UNILATERAL declarations of independence.”**

The exercise of sovereignty by a people (specifically, through a declaration of independence) **does NOT require PRIOR RECOGNITION or EXTERNAL APPROVAL.**
Sovereignty is NOT contingent upon external validation.

4) International Court of Justice (ICJ) (Advisory Opinion on Namibia; 21.06.1971)

Prg53: “The Court is bound to take into account the fact that the concepts embodied in Article 22 of the Covenant-“**the strenuous conditions of the modern world**” and “**the well-being and development**” of the peoples concerned-were not static, but were by definition evolutionary, as also, therefore, was the concept of the “sacred trust”... **the ultimate objective of the sacred trust was the self-determination and independence of the peoples concerned.**

<https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/53/053-19710621-ADV-01-00-EN.pdf> (judgment)

ICJ: “the continued presence of South Africa in Namibia was **ILLEGAL** and that South Africa was under an obligation to withdraw its administration immediately. States

Members of the United Nations were under an obligation to recognize the **ILLEGALITY** of South Africa's presence in Namibia and the **INVALIDITY** of South Africa's acts on behalf of or concerning Namibia, and to **refrain from any acts implying recognition of the legality of, or lending support or assistance to, such presence and administration.** It was incumbent upon **States which were NOT Members of the United Nations** to give assistance in the action which had been taken by the United Nations about Namibia.
<https://www.icj-cij.org/case/53> (summary)

Since the situation is **COMPLETELY** different in the case of **TRNC**, **the international courts** (ECtHR; European Court of Human Rights) **and country courts** (the **USA**; the **UK**) **recognize the legality of TRNC and its legislation**, see:

ECtHR's (European Court of Human Rights) decisions:

ECtHR (02.07.2013): In north of Cyprus island, the laws of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus are valid (TRNC DOES HAVE jurisdiction in north of Cyprus island) (See section 2.1)

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-122907>

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22sort%22:%5B%22kupdate%20Descending%22%5D,%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-122907%22%5D%7D>

ECtHR (04.01.2011): ALL the people of Rep. of Cyprus (even the President of RoC) MUST apply to the LEGAL SYSTEM of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC) about an issue related with north Cyprus in order to take their cases to the ECtHR (See section 2.2)

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-103100>

[http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/sites/eng/Pages/search.aspx#{"fulltext":\["Chrysostomos"\],"documentcollectionid2":\["CASELAW"\],"itemid":\["001-103100"\]}](http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/sites/eng/Pages/search.aspx#{)

ECtHR (02.09.2015): The Courts of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus are INDEPENDENT and IMPARTIAL (See section 2.3)

<http://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-155000>

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22sort%22:%5B%22kupdate%20Descending%22%5D,%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-155000%22%5D%7D>

ECtHR (25.06.2024): The Reasons why JUDICIAL LEGAL SYSTEM of TRNC in Northern Cyprus under the ECtHR framework is LEGAL in ECHR whereas LEGAL SYSTEMS in Transnistria, Abkhazia, and Crimea are ILLEGAL in in ECHR:

- i) TRNC DOMESTIC LAW WAS BASED ON THE ANGLO-SAXON LEGAL TRADITION
- ii) THE CONTINUED APPLICATION OF PRE-EXISTING CYPRIOT LAW BY TURKISH CYPRIOT AUTHORITIES AFTER 1974 (See section 2.4)

<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/?i=001-235139>

The USA's Federal Court and the USA's Court of Appeals decision:

The United States Federal Court (09.10.2014):

“the TRNC purportedly operates as a **DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC** with a president, prime minister, **LEGISLATURE AND JUDICIARY**...The TRNC is **NOT** vulnerable to a lawsuit in Washington.”

((Courthouse News Center 13.10.2014: Property Spat Over Turk-Controlled Cyprus Fails:

<https://www.courthousenews.com/property-spat-over-turk-controlled-cyprus-fails/>

USA's Federal Court: Michali Toumazou, Nicolas Kantzilaris and Maroulla Tompozou versus Republic of Turkey and **Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus**:

<http://dockets.justia.com/docket/district-of-columbia/dcdce/1:2009cv01967/139002>

USA's Federal Court Toumazou et al v. Republic of Turkey and **Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus**:

<https://docs.justia.com/cases/federal/district-courts/district-of-columbia/dcdce/1:2009cv01967/139002/53>)))

The USA Court of Appeals REJECTED Greek Cypriot Toumazou's appeal (15.01.2016):

<https://media.cadc.uscourts.gov/judgments/docs/2016/01/14-7170-1593754.pdf>

After the US Federal Court called and qualified TRNC as “Democratic Republic” and the USA Court of Appeals affirmed the decision, The United States Secretary of State has started to describe the **TRNC** as **the Area Administered by Turkish Cypriots**:

<https://www.state.gov/reports/2022-report-on-international-religious-freedom/cyprus/area-administered-by-turkish-cypriots/>

The United Kingdom High Court (03.02.2017):

“There was **NO DUTY** in UK law upon the Government **TO REFRAIN FROM RECOGNISING NORTHERN CYPRUS**. The United Nations itself works with Northern Cyprus law enforcement agencies and facilitates co-operation between the two parts of the island...**The cooperation between the UK police and legal institutions in Northern Cyprus is LAWFUL.**”

<http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2017/02/03/criminals-fleeing-british-justice-can-no-longer-use-cyprus-safe>

http://ambamarblearch-media.com/sites/default/files/dpp_files/TT.pdf, Page6.

5) Permanent Court of International Justice (PCIJ); Legal Status of Eastern Greenland (05.04.1933; PCIJ Series A/B. No 53)

The Sovereignty of Eastern Greenland was given by PICJ to Denmark since:

1. The **continuous and peaceful exercise of sovereignty** over Greenland resulted in the title towards Denmark.
2. The Court made the Ihlen declaration binding thereby conferring the sovereignty to Denmark.

https://www.academia.edu/42041524/Legal_Status_of_Eastern_Greenland

(see Page9)

Hence:

1. The **continuous and peaceful exercise of sovereignty over the area claimed** results in the title (**sovereignty**) towards the Claimant country.
2. **The declaration/decision of the de facto non-controlling country (affecting negatively to the arguments and claims of the de facto non-controller) is binding upon the de facto non-controller.**

When applied to TRNC:

1. TRNC exercise **continuous and peaceful exercise of sovereignty** over Northern Cyprus: The title (sovereignty) of Northern Cyprus belongs to TRNC.
2. The Court of Republic of Cyprus (Greek Cypriot court) decided that the courts of Republic of Cyprus cannot judge Türkiye about a property in Northern Cyprus. **The**

decision of the Court of (de facto non-controller) Rep. of Cyprus affecting negatively to the arguments and claims of (de facto non-controller) Rep. of Cyprus IS binding upon the de facto non-controller Rep. of Cyprus.

(see: Ioannis Sherkesavvas, Katina Savva Kounama case: The decision of Court of Appeals of Republic of Cyprus dated 11.2024 cancelled the decision of the first-degree court of Rep. of Cyprus against Türkiye for the compensation for the loss of usage about a property (in Kyrenia) in Northern Cyprus: This decision of a court of RoC (that negatively affects the sovereignty claims of RoC over Northern Cyprus) blasted RoC's own sovereignty claim.

Note: Even if the Court of Appeals of Republic of Cyprus had decided affirmatively the decision of the first-degree court of Rep. of Cyprus against Türkiye for the compensation for the loss of usage about a property in Northern Cyprus, that decision would have been illegal since TRNC's jurisdiction in Northern Cyprus is legal in international law (see: ECtHR's 2024-decision).

Here the issue is that a de facto non-controller country (here:Rep. of Cyprus) cannot decide against itself (Rep. of Cyprus) on a sovereignty issue irrespective of what international law says.

[11b] TURKISH CYPRIOT NATION IS PEOPLE

The properties of "People" (human collectivity or a group that has the right for eligibility to statehood; the group that has the right to **INTERNAL** self-determination):

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (1966) (article 27):

- 1) A historical territorial connection, on which territory the group forms a majority,
 - 2) A common history,
 - 3) Common ethnic identity or origin,
 - 4) A common language,
 - 5) A common culture
 - 6) A common religion or ideology
 - 7) The belief of being a distinct person distinguishable from any other person.
- (Cassese, A. 1995. Self-determination of people. Legal reappraisal. Henkin editor. Cambridge University Press, p98).

Judge Cançado Trindade (UN ICJ 2010 Kosovo Advisory Decision):

(a) Common background of **ethnicity**, common **language**, common **religion**, common **history**, common **cultural heritage**;

(b) **Territorial integrity of the area claimed**;

(c) The subjective element of the group's self-conscious perception as a **distinct** "people", able to form a viable political entity;

(d) **Common suffering**

<https://www.icj-cij.org/index.php/node/141829>